

Nice couple, funny couple, happy couple: emotional intelligence, humor style, and relationship satisfaction

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 6, 2023

Revised May 9, 2024

Accepted May 18, 2024

Keywords:

Beneficial humor style

Emotional intelligence

Humor styles

Mental wellbeing

Relationship satisfaction

Social exchange theory

ABSTRACT

This study explores the interplay of emotional intelligence (EI), beneficial humor styles (BHS), and relationship satisfaction (RS) within romantic relationships. Drawing on the social exchange theory, it examines whether BHS mediate the relationship between EI and RS. Data was collected from individuals aged 18 to 65 in romantic relationships, and analyses were conducted using bootstrapping methods. Results reveal a significant positive direct effect of EI on RS. However, the mediation analysis suggests that BHS do not mediate the relationship between EI and RS, indicating that EI's impact on RS remains independent of humor styles. These findings underscore the distinct and substantial roles of EI and BHS in predicting RS. While both factors contribute to RS, they do so independently. This study enhances our understanding of the multifaceted factors influencing romantic relationship dynamics and highlights the importance of emotional intelligence and humor styles in fostering relationship satisfaction. Limitations include self-report measures and a limited age range, suggesting the need for further research to explore these dynamics across diverse populations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Relationship satisfaction has been identified as a significant protective factor for mental health. A longitudinal analysis conducted in the UK reported that lower mental health is associated with lower satisfaction with partners [1]. This study also highlighted a potential 'vicious circle' between satisfaction with partners and mental health for males, suggesting that investment in mental health provision can improve satisfaction with partners, which in turn will further enhance health and well-being. Another study reported that relationship satisfaction (RS) is significantly, positively related to all six domains of the health-Promoting Lifestyle Profile II (HPLP-II) [2], with the strongest correlations found between relationship satisfaction and stress management, interpersonal relations, and spiritual growth. This indicates that individuals who are more satisfied with their relationships engage in more health-promoting behaviors, which can contribute to better mental health [3]. Furthermore, social connection, which includes relationship satisfaction, is the strongest protective factor for depression [4]. Confirming that, studies on mental health among adults across age groups suggested that the sense that one matters and is connected to others significantly lowered the symptoms anxiety [5] depression [6], and even the development of suicide ideation [7].

In addition to relationship satisfaction, humor, and emotional intelligence have also been identified as protective factors for mental health. A study published in *Frontiers in Psychology* found a significant

positive correlation between emotional intelligence, flourishing, and positive humor styles [8]. This suggests that individuals with higher emotional intelligence are more likely to use positive or adaptive humor styles, which can contribute to better mental health. Another study reported that emotional intelligence is a protective resource that can buffer the effects of stressors in certain contexts, including the experience of stress due to interpersonal relationships through social media stress [9]. This highlights the role of emotional intelligence in managing stress and promoting mental health.

The quality of relationships has a profound impact on an individual's mental well-being [10]. Recent trends indicate a global increase in divorce rates a situation further exacerbated by the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic [11]. This study seeks to address these issues by probing the connection between emotional intelligence (EI), beneficial humor styles (BHS), and relationship satisfaction (RS); the objective of this study is to ascertain whether BHS mediate the relationship between EI and RS. The social exchange theory by Emerson [12] forms the theoretical framework for this study, focusing on understanding relationship satisfaction. It emphasizes the "cost-effect" algorithm individuals employ to weigh the benefits and risks of a relationship. According to Emerson's theory, partners in a relationship tend to assess their benefit and cost of the relationship they are in; when they can perceive an acceptable balance between the two, they would likely to be more satisfied with their relationship [13]. In general, RS encompasses an individual's overall sense of happiness and contentment within a romantic union. Extensive It was established that heightened RS [14] is intricately linked to enhanced physical and psychological well-being. Apart from that, a plethora of factors exert influence over relationship satisfaction, spanning personality traits, attachment styles, cultural nuances, and the quality of communication. The latter, communication skills, play pivotal role in supporting other factors that have been developed between the partners such as intimacy, commitment, and passion within the realm of romantic relationships [15]. Communication skills, the ability to present, obtain, accept, or turn down one another's idea with minimum conflict in various setting, is significantly linked to EI [16], individuals with adequate EI are likely to have stronger communication skills that keep the relationship satisfying. The statement was also supported by the report that individuals endowed with higher emotional intelligence tend to experience elevated relationship satisfaction levels and possess superior conflict resolution skills [17].

It was also established that individuals with higher EI tend to know how to integrate humor to maintain and improve hope, resilience, and relationships satisfaction [18], [19]. Supporting that, a meta-analysis conducted by Dođru [20] examined the links between EI and various outcomes. The study reported that numerous studies established that EI positively related to RS and negatively related to stress disorders. Nevertheless, the relationship between EI and RS might not happen directly, as having excellent people skills alone might not solve certain types of chronic conflicts in the relationship, as mentioned by Sierra *et al.* [15]; some studies suggested that the usage of humor in interpersonal communication improve the quality of the relationship between the individuals involved [19].

Furhtermore, the proper usage of humor might refer to the proper choice of the humor styles to enhance the relationship; this ability to choose the proper styles of humor is reported to be closely tied to their EI, which in turn affects their social engagement and their own wellbeing [19]. Humor styles refer to the various ways in which individuals use humor in their social interactions and communication. These styles can be categorized into different types, with each type reflecting a distinct approach to humor. There are various humor styles such as i) Affiliative, involves using humor to enhance social bonds and build connections with others, ii) Self-Enhancing Humor, involves finding humor in one's own experiences and situations, allowing individuals to cope with stress and adversity by finding amusement in life's challenge, iii) Aggressive Humor: such as sarcasm, teasing, and mockery, often aimed at belittling or embarrassing someone, iv) Self-Defeating Humor, making oneself the target of jokes and self-deprecating humor. It is done to downplay their achievements or make fun of their own flaws to gain social acceptance. v) Enhancing humor combines positive elements of affiliative and self-enhancing humor. It involves using humor to uplift others' spirits, boost morale, and create a positive environment while also finding amusement in life's ups and downs. The aforementioned humor styles are not mutually exclusive, and individuals may use a combination of them in different social situations. The choice of humor style can significantly impact social interactions, relationships, and overall well-being, depending on the context and the preferences of those involved [19].

In this current study, we focus on the BHS as they foster a positive relational atmosphere and promote a deeper connection between partners [21], and it requires adequate EI for an individual to come up to employ BHS in their daily conversation [22]. In other words, EI intertwines with the utilization of adaptive humor styles, such as BHS, and utilize it to improve the quality of their relationship with others, which in turn, elevate the mental wellbeing of theirs and their partners' [23]. The aforementioned studies suggested that individuals with higher EI tend to be able to utilize adaptive humor styles, specifically BHS, to elevate their RS. Based on that, we aim to investigate whether EI has a significant direct contribution on RS or is the presence of BHS is required to maintain and improve RS. Figure 1 illustrates our hypothetical model.

Figure 1. The mediation hypothesis

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants

Our study purposively targeted individuals aged 18 to 65 involved in romantic relationships, including engagement, marriage, or cohabitation in any form, and not diagnosed with any psychological or mental disorder. This wide range of age group was selected as we would like to include any type and duration of relationship; and a couple in their twenties might have different RS conditions when compared to a couple in their forties; nevertheless, albeit the different conditions to make their relationship satisfying, the role of EI and BHS should not significantly vary among the age group [19]. Based on G*power sample size calculator, 90 respondents were suggested. As mentioned, non-probability sampling, specifically purposive and snowball sampling, which are suggested to efficiently study a population with specific experience [24], such as being or have been in relationship. Following the reception of the written permission to use the measuring instruments from their rightful owners, ethical clearance from the Ethics Review Board of the Faculty of Psychology and Social sciences, University of Cyberjaya was obtained (#FPSS/202w3/3039). the participants were recruited by using social media and other electronic means of communication; the link to the Google form containing our informed content form, demographic questionnaire, and scales to measure all the variable, was distributed to the participants through the same way. The participants were voluntarily and consensually providing their data, as well as helped to recruit other participants within the inclusion criteria.

2.2. Measures

The research instrument was a survey questionnaire with four major sections after the demography questionnaire:

2.2.1. Relationship assessment scale (RAS)

This scale measured the degree of relationship satisfaction. Developed by Hendrick in 1988 [25], the RAS is a unidimensional self-report questionnaire. A five-point Likert Scale ranging from "Extremely Unsatisfied" to "Extremely Satisfied" assessed respondents' satisfaction. Items 4 and 7 were reverse scored. The participant's score was the accumulation of responses, with higher scores indicating greater relationship satisfaction (Cronbach's Alpha reliability value of 0.79).

2.2.2. Humor styles questionnaire (HSQ)

To measure beneficial humor styles, a modified version of the HSQ by Martin *et al.* [26] was used. The instrument had 16 items, including 6 reverse-scored ones, assessing affiliative and self-enhancing humor styles. Respondents used a seven-point Likert scale ranging from "Totally Disagree" to "Totally Agree." Scores across the affiliative and self-enhancing domains were combined for the final score (Cronbach's alpha reliability value of 0.58).

2.2.3. Brief emotional intelligence scale (BEIS-10)

Emotional intelligence was measured using the BEIS-10, a shorter version adapted from the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test [27]. The scale included 10 items across five subsets and employed a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." The final emotional intelligence score was calculated from individual item scores (Cronbach's alpha reliability value of 0.88).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data was analyzed using the bootstrap method with 5,000 samples, at 95% confidence interval using PROCESS MACRO model 4 in SPSS. Bootstrap method was chosen as its creator, Efron [28] has proven in many studies that it is a powerful statistical technique that uses random sampling with replacement to estimate a population parameter. This method is particularly useful for testing mediation hypotheses for several reasons; firstly, the bootstrap method does not assume that the data are normally distributed [29], making it more suitable for small sample sizes [30]. This is a significant advantage over other methods that require the assumption of normality, such as multiple regression or Sobel test [31], [32].

Secondly, bootstrapping allows for the estimation of the sampling distribution of almost any statistic using random sampling methods [33]. This flexibility makes it an excellent tool for exploring complex relationships, such as those found in mediation and moderation analyses [34]. To execute Bootstrap method, we utilized PROCESS Macro 4 for SPSS by Hayes [35], with model 4 for mediation analysis. PROCESS Macro for SPSS was chosen as it is an effective and efficient tool for analyzing mediation hypotheses [34]. The PROCESS Macro is widely used in various fields, including behavioral sciences, business research, medicine, and public health. Furthermore, it is considered to be more efficient and effective than structural equation modeling [36], as it makes no assumptions about the shape of the population distribution or the sampling distribution [37]. This is particularly useful when dealing with small sample sizes or non-normal distributions. Secondly, bootstrapping allows for the estimation of the sampling distribution of almost any statistic using random sampling methods. This flexibility makes it an excellent tool for exploring complex relationships, such as those found in mediation analyses.

3.1. Results

Table 1 displays the results of the direct effect of EI on RS. The analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between EI and RS ($B=0.3797$, $p<0.01^{**}$). Table 1 suggested that the direct effect of EI on RS is significant ($p<0.01^{**}$), indicating that emotional intelligence predicts the relationship satisfaction. This finding is in line with the previous recent findings such as the ones by Rastogi [8], Józefacka *et al.* [15], Samad and Mahmud [17], Karahan *et al.* [23]. These uniformed findings established the positive contribution of EI on RS in various settings. Furthermore, Table 2 presents the results of the mediation analysis exploring the indirect effect of EI on RS through the mediator, BHS. The analysis indicates that the indirect effect of EI through BHS is not significant ($B=0.0264$, $p>0.05$), and the confidence interval includes both positive and negative values. Table 2 summarizes the results for the Indirect Effect ($X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$): The mediation of BHS between EI and RS is not supported, as indicated by the non-significant p-value and the confidence interval including both positive and negative values, which does not support our previous hypothesis.

Table 1. Direct effect of EI on RS – bootstrap for coefficients

Variable	B	Std. error	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% CI
EI	0.3797	0.0298	<.01	[0.3212, 0.4383]

Table 2. Indirect effect of EI on RS through BHS – bootstrap for coefficients

Variable	B	Std. error	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% CI
BHS	0.0264	0.0155	>.05	[-0.0071, 0.0539]

3.2. Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that the usage of BHS does not mediate the relationship between EI and RS. In other words, while both EI and BHS individually have significant associations with RS, BHS does not act as an intermediary in enhancing the effect of EI on RS. These results suggest that the impact of EI on RS remains direct and is not contingent on the presence or level of BHS. This implies that individuals with higher EI are likely to experience greater relationship satisfaction regardless of their humor styles, highlighting the unique and independent role of emotional intelligence in fostering satisfying romantic relationships.

Comparing these findings with previous studies, it is evident that emotional intelligence consistently emerges as a significant predictor of relationship satisfaction. High EI levels are associated with better conflict resolution, reduced aggression, and enhanced overall relationship quality, aligning with the results of this stud. The positive contribution of EI on RS is further corroborated by studies demonstrating its correlation with higher relationship quality and better social coordination [17]. The present study reinforces the idea that EI plays a pivotal role in shaping relationship satisfaction.

On the other hand, beneficial humor styles have been widely recognized as factors contributing to greater relationship satisfaction. Positive humor, affiliative humor styles, and self-enhancing humor have all been linked to increased relationship quality and satisfaction. These studies emphasize the importance of humor in maintaining positive relationships. However, in contrast to the existing literature, this study did not find a mediating role for BHS in the relationship between EI and RS. It suggests that while both EI and BHS contribute independently to RS, they do not interact in a way that amplifies their combined effect.

In summary, this study underscores the distinct and significant influences of emotional intelligence and beneficial humor styles on relationship satisfaction. While EI remains a robust predictor of RS, BHS, despite its well-documented positive impact on RS, does not mediate the relationship between EI and RS. This implies that individuals with higher emotional intelligence can experience higher relationship satisfaction regardless of their specific humor styles, highlighting the multifaceted nature of factors influencing romantic relationship.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the independent roles of emotional intelligence and beneficial humor styles in predicting relationship satisfaction. While there was no evidence of mediation, both emotional intelligence and humor styles emerged as important factors in understanding the dynamics of romantic relationships. One limitation of this study is that it relied on self-report measures for emotional intelligence, beneficial humor styles, and relationship satisfaction, which can be subject to response bias and may not fully capture participants' actual behaviors and experiences. Additionally, the study's sample was limited to a specific age range (18-65 years), which may not fully represent the diversity of romantic relationships across different age groups. As a closing anecdote related to the title of this paper, we would like to conclude that nice people do not have to be funny to be satisfied with their relationship.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express the sincere gratitude to the ethic review board of the Faculty of Psychology and Social Sciences, University of Cyberjaya for the ethic review, clearance (# FPSS/202w3/3039), as well as to the Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia for the support on the publication of this study.

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